

THE USE OF THE SPORTS SPHERE OF THE UZBEK SSR BY THE SOVIET AUTHORITIES IN ITS VARIOUS INTERESTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13827384>

Annotation

This thesis covered the cases of the use of Soviet power in the field of Sports Of The Uzbek SSR in its various interests. In particular, it has been cited that the working class used precisely the field of sports in increasing their ability to work, in ensuring defensive strength, in increasing the "Cotton plan". It can be seen that the Soviet authorities, as cadres of the sports sphere of the Uzbek SSR, mainly attracted representatives of other nationalities, on the contrary, a small number of national cadres were taken into this sphere.

Keywords: Soviet power, Uzbek SSR, higher Soviet of physical education, efficiency of workability, strengthening defense, "Cotton plan".

The central executive of Uzbekistan appoints Fayzulla Khojaev¹ – chairman of the Supreme Soviet of physical education through his decision . It can be seen that the appointment of the chairman of the SNK (Council of the committee of Ministers) of the Uzbek SSR - Fayzulla Khojaev – as chairman of the Supreme Soviet of physical education of the Uzbek SSR – aims to spread the ideology of Soviet power-to use physical education as the main element. The information letter of 18.01.1927, sent to Fayzulla Khodzhaev, chairman of the Supreme Soviet of physical education of the Uzbek SSR, quoted: "you will be informed that on our side a total of 42 raion instructors were asked to be allocated from the Republic, but the raion instructors were not allocated. It was not possible to do this due to the insufficient focus of the Regional Executive Committee on Physical Education²".

The use of the sports field in improving efficiency of workability. In the draft resolution of the Presidium of the Central Executive Committee of the OSSR on strengthening physical education, it is stated: "Let the USSR allocate more than all the funds available at the disposal of the Soviet states in order to increase the labor capacity of the worker-peasant masses, at the core of socialist construction in all its folk farms. In addition, the next task that is currently facing physical education is to spread widely through the deep Organization of the

¹ "Правда востока" newspaper// 28.05.1925y. №115.

² Uzbekistan national archive P-86 fund, I-inventory, 4534-case, 4-page

hardworking avom physical movement and strengthen this movement in the villages³".

Also included in the text of the project is the following: "physical education should be used comprehensively as a mass factor in increasing labor production. At the same time, the Union of the SSR is required to be used both in defense issues, in increasing the military capacity of the Red Army and in the training of the country's laborers⁴".

The use of the sports field in ensuring defensive strength. All-Union Trade Union Medium. In the cultural assembly of the Asian Bureau dated 8.02.1928, in the Resolution No. 130 on "issues of Physical Education and sports in trade unions", it is listed as follows: "For the reason of physical education – the role of the state in strengthening the possibility of Defense (the fact that workers-dexkans are sent to the Red Army in full physical-military terms) deserves recognition." Nevertheless, the cultural assembly also informs that the following deficiency exists. That is, the work of militarization of Physical Education is not enough, and the state of Shooting Sports is still in a weak state⁵.

The appeal of the Supreme Soviet of physical education to all Soviets of the Supreme Soviet of physical education of the USSR on the militarization of physical education reads: "by militarization of physical education, it is necessary to understand the use of physical education for the purpose of defense of the country. Based on the goals and Essence Set in physical education, the task, funds and methods, it can be confirmed that the militarization of physical education of the working population is fully consistent as a component of the adopted physical education construction system⁶".

Заравшон округида Жисмоний тарбия ҳолати ва Жисмоний тарбия Совети ҳаракатлари бўйича ҳисоботида қуйидагилар келтирилган(Кермене шахри, 1928 йил бўйича):

"Чақириққача бўлганлар билан ишлаш суст олиб борилмоқда. Совет Жисмоний тарбия ғоясини чақириққача ёшдагилар орасида ташвиқот қилиш яхши амалга оширилмаяпти⁷".

Documents on Uzbek personnel working in the field of sports. The information letter of May 15, 1928 on the state of affairs of the Soviet of physical education of the district under the Andijan County Executive Committee states the following: "The disadvantages are that the big mistake made in spreading

³ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 fund, 1-inventory, 6886-case, 23-page

Uzbekistan national archive P-86 fund, 1-inventory, 6886-case, 24-page

⁵ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 fund, 1-inventory, 5292-case, 3-page

⁶ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 фонд, 1- inventory, 5298-case, 2-page

⁷ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 фонд, 1- inventory, 5298-case, 50-page

physical education in the village was the fact that the only Uzbek instructor (Atamuratov) was taken from the work of Physical Education. But, despite the request of the Supreme Soviet of physical education, he was dismissed, and now he does not have Hech to send him to the village instead⁸.

A letter of appeal to the Supreme Soviet of physical education from the Samarkand County Council of Physical Education (Samarkand County Soset of Physical Education on behalf of deputy chairman - Ponikarov) dated August 16, 1925 included: "Kholmiraev was working as an assistant physical education instructor at the Uzbek maorif Institute, but he fell on the list of reduction of workers and is going to Tashkent for Cotton Committee courses. He is the only one in Samarkand who is able to do physical education training. I inform you that you will be taken away from him and in return he agreed to remain as a student in the Uzbek maorif instiuti and at the same time engage in the Old Town 3 times a week⁹".

A contract containing the above items is concluded, which tells him that it was only evazi who was left at work to fulfill his obligation to work in Physical Education for 3 hours a week in the Old City¹⁰.

The use of the sports field in the implementation of the "Cotton plan". This is how Fergana County is written in the document sent to physical education from the Supreme Soviet of Physical Education (on behalf of the deputy secretary in charge of the Supreme Soviet of Physical Education – Shishkin) : "At the time of holding a holiday(physical education holiday) in the county: it is necessary to introduce physical education practitioners to the cotton program, send the physical education organization to fulfill the Cotton plan, organize a concourse on the best organized rural physical education circles in the regions, especially in the cotton raions (Sovkhoz, collective farm, young peasant schools)¹¹".

References:

1. "Правда востока" newspaper// 28.05.1925y. №115.
2. Uzbekistan national archive P-86 fund materials

⁸ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 фонд, 1- inventory, 5285-case, 64-page

⁹ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 фонд, 1- inventory, 2596-case, 35-page

¹⁰ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 фонд, 1- inventory, 2596-case, 36-page

¹¹ Uzbekistan national archive P-86 fund, 1-inventory, 5961-case, 18-page

